

Bosonic Propagations and Cyclic Groups – 8 Theory

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Abstract:

By using the first representation of the coupling constant series, it is possible to construct a cyclic group with the majestic (3) as generator for the propagation of bosonic fields, which are infinite in kind. The cyclic group is than indicating that the sub elements of the group must by cycles themselves. Such a simple idea can allow us a profound insight into the nature and geometrical shape of bosons.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (0)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.11)$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

Cyclic groups in mathematics are represented by the following, if a set of elements is generated by one single element, than we have a cyclic group. Since all the bosonic fields or net variations in the 8T are generated by the same element, i.e. the majestic (3), than there is in this framework an infinite cyclic group. Define the majestic three as the generator:

$$(3) \rightarrow \mathcal{M}$$

$$\mathcal{B} = \{N_1 = (+3)\mathcal{M}, N_2 = +(5)\mathcal{M} \dots\} \quad (3.1)$$

By representing the propagation in such fashion, we can state that since the bosons are propagations are part of an infinite cyclic group, the sub elements of that cyclic group are cycles themselves. We have proven the representation of the coupling constant series in the thesis:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (3.11)$$

$$\mathcal{B} = \{N_1 = (+3)\mathcal{M}, N_2 = +(\gamma)\mathcal{M} \dots\} \quad (3.12)$$

Therefore, that is a proof that bosonic net variations are cycles, or in physical theories, bosonic particles are in fact closed strings. That is because they are generated by the same element.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)